

Anglicisms in CREA: A Quantitative Analysis in Spanish Newspapers¹

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Resumen

*El uso de anglicismos en la lengua española hoy en día es perceptible en diversos ámbitos. En este artículo se analizará uno de ellos: la prensa contemporánea. Se realizará una búsqueda de un total de 2198 anglicismos en el **Corpus de Referencia del Español Actual** (CREA), aplicando filtros de fecha (2001 – 2004), medio (prensa) y localización geográfica (España). Los resultados se ordenarán de acuerdo con la fuente en la que se hayan obtenido (i.e. el periódico) para así establecer una clasificación de medios de comunicación escritos según la frecuencia con la que aparecen anglicismos entre sus páginas.*

Palabras clave: *anglicismos; periódicos españoles; lingüística de corpus; frecuencia de uso; prensa; préstamos*

Abstract

*The use of Anglicisms in the Spanish language nowadays is noticeable in different spheres. One of them will be analysed in this article: the contemporary press. I will look up a total number of 2198 Anglicisms in the **Corpus de Referencia del Español Actual** (CREA), applying several filters: date (2001 – 2004), medium*

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(press), and geographical location (Spain). Results will be arranged according to the source where they appear (i.e. the newspaper) in order to establish a classification of written mass media in relation to the frequency with which they employ Anglicisms in their texts.

Key words: *Anglicisms; Spanish newspapers; corpus linguistics; frequency of use; press; loanwords*

1. Introduction

The growing use of Anglicisms in different languages has been a pervasive phenomenon for the last decades. Spanish is not an exception, and this linguistic issue has been approached by a number of authors, mainly from the 1950s onwards.³ As Rodríguez Medina (2016, p. 128) states, “[t]he study of Anglicisms in Spanish as a complex result of language contact and cultural globalization has increasingly caught scholars’ attention”. In their work, the adoption of words of English origin is treated from different perspectives and in the various levels of the system (phonological, morphological, lexical, semantic, syntactic, phraseological). However, the resources available for these researchers did not make it possible to complete the glossaries of Anglicisms they elaborated with enough data as to support the explanations they provided. As time has gone by, large data banks or corpora⁴ have been compiled, solving to a great extent those methodological problems of the past. In fact, these corpora “allow us to contrast and corroborate some of the suggestions made - but rarely proved with robust corpus evidence- in the specialized literature on Anglicisms in Spanish” (Oncins-Martínez, 2012, p. 236). In this study I will employ the *Corpus de Referencia del Español Actual* (CREA),⁵ a corpus of contemporary Spanish collected by the Real Academia Española, in order to analyse the frequency with which Anglicisms appear in

³ “Las primeras investigaciones referidas más concretamente al anglicismo en español datan de mediados del siglo XX” (García Morales, González Cruz, Luján García, & Rodríguez Medina, 2016, p. 38).

⁴ A corpus is, in McEnery, Xiao, & Tono's (2006, p. 5) words, “a collection of (1) *machine-readable* (2) *authentic* texts (including transcripts of spoken data) which is (3) *sampled* to be (4) *representative* of a particular language or language variety” (original italics).

⁵ *Present-Day Spanish Reference Corpus* (my translation).

the different sources included in the medium “Newspapers” from 2001 to 2004. Therefore, I aim to carry out an analysis of the sources of the Spanish press in terms of Anglicisms employed in each of them at the beginning of the 21st century. Furthermore, the following hypotheses will be tested:

- There are some sources where no Anglicisms are used.
- In relation to ideological differences, *El País* contains more Anglicisms than *La Razón* and *ABC*.
- As* and *Marca*, being newspapers specialized in sports, are the sources in which more tokens of Anglicisms appear.

As far as the selection of the corpus is concerned, I have decided to use journalistic texts in the present research because the press is characterized by closely recording the state of the language a people possesses at each moment and, at the same time, spreading the current neologisms that have recently been coined (Casado Velarde, 2015; del Pino Romero, 2013; Furiassi, 2008; Luján García, 1999; Medina López, 2004; Oncins-Martínez, 2012).

2. Review of the literature

In 2012, a volume containing a selection of papers delivered at a seminar on the occasion of the 10th International Conference of the *European Society for the Study of English (ESSE)*, held in Turin (Italy) in 2010, was published under the title *The Anglicization of European Lexis* (Furiassi, Pulcini, & Rodríguez González, 2012). In this book, a useful tool is applied to the study of the presence of Anglicisms in different languages: corpus linguistics. This methodology makes it possible to work with huge amounts of texts, thus obtaining a large number of instances of words of English origin. As a matter of fact, “[i]n the study of Anglicisms, corpora are indispensable because they offer up-to-date source material from which new Anglicisms or new meanings/senses of Anglicisms may be detected. Through corpus-based research it is possible to (...) obtain information about frequency, period of adoption, usage context and authentic examples” (Furiassi et al., 2012, p. 18). Therefore, *The Anglicization of European Lexis* aims, among other purposes, to “compare approaches and methodologies (especially corpus-based) for

assessing the lexical impact of the English language on a European scale” (Furiassi et al., 2012, p. 1).

The chapter devoted to Anglicisms in Spanish within this volume, by José Luis Oncins-Martínez,⁶ makes use of the *Corpus Diacrónico del Español* CORDE (Diachronic Corpus of Spanish) and the *Corpus de Referencia del Español Actual* –CREA, both compiled by the Real Academia Española. They constitute extremely useful resources for the purpose of studying the entrance of Anglicisms in the Spanish language since, as stated in the Introduction to the present article (*vide supra*), they fill a gap highlighted by several authors, i.e. the lack of real and reliable data, of data “that is accurately dated and abundant enough” (Oncins-Martínez, 2012, p. 218). Indeed, these electronic materials “offer sounder (...) ways of exploring and characterizing Anglicisms in Spanish” and they “can help us track down the occurrence of foreign usages more systematically and assess the extent of their presence in Spanish more accurately” (Oncins-Martínez, 2012, p. 217). By using them, the author uncovers that there are Spanish words nowadays employed more and more frequently with a sense taken from English than with their traditional Spanish meanings. However, these semantic Anglicisms go unnoticed by the RAE, which does not include their new senses in its *Dictionary* (22nd edition, 2001). Moreover, Oncins-Martínez deals with the calquing of several phraseological units that are proved to have been adopted from English into Spanish by means of a corpus-based analysis (of CORDE and CREA).

3. Methodology

In this article I carry out a study based on the Anglicisms collected by Delia Rodríguez Segura in her PhD thesis (Universidad de Almería, 1998. ISBN:

⁶ A previous article by this author (Oncins-Martínez, 2009) constitutes a pioneering work in terms of the application of corpus linguistics methods to the study of Anglicisms in the Spanish press. Specifically, it presents a case study: “the adverb *dramáticamente*, as it is taking on the new sense ‘espectacularmente’ under the influence of English *dramatically*” (p.115). Another piece of research that employs an electronically held corpus (CREA) when analysing the use of Anglicisms (in this case, those related to the sports field) in Spanish is Balteiro Fernández (2011).

84-8240-156-4). I have chosen this work because its author provides us with the most comprehensive list of Anglicisms in Spanish from recent times I have found in the literature. First, I make a selection of the words she compiles based on a series of criteria that will be stated below. Then, I perform searches in the *Corpus de Referencia del Español Actual* (CREA), and finally I obtain data on the sources in relation to the Anglicisms that are found in each of them.

Rodríguez Segura (1998) includes a list of Anglicisms she found in different mass media (radio, television, newspapers...) during the 1990s. She classifies them, makes reference to several dictionaries and gives a brief explanation on each foreign word. In relation to the examples, the author illustrates every Anglicism with two or three instances. Therefore, the contextual information in relation to these foreign words in use is very limited (there is no access to the whole range of varied linguistic contexts in which the word can be employed), since, as has been stated above, the means available for researchers at the end of the 90s did not allow the compilation of a wider sample of real uses.

However, nowadays corpus linguistics constitutes a useful tool for analysing a given phenomenon in a great number of texts, offering the possibility of studying it in an enormous variety of different co-texts and providing us with data that makes it possible to obtain frequencies of use. For instance, in Furiassi (2008), this methodology is employed to discover the actual presence of Anglicisms in the Italian language. In this case, frequency counts carried out on a corpus of newspaper texts provide interesting insights into the real “incidence of non-adapted Anglicisms in Italian” (Furiassi, 2008, p. 313) and does have positive implications for lexicographic practice.

Therefore, taking Rodríguez Segura's (1998) list as a starting point, I decided to look for these Anglicisms in the Spanish contemporary press in order to come by with real cases in which they were employed at a recent period of time. First of all, it must be stated that I made a selection of the Anglicisms provided by Rodríguez Segura (1998) in the Appendix I of her thesis, leaving aside the following ones:

- Lexical Anglicisms that she collected only from oral mass media (she gives their phonetic transcription and their English spelling form or the

standard Spanish one. Thus, since I am going to distinguish among orthographic varieties, these cases are irrelevant for my purposes)

- What Rodríguez Segura (1998) calls “calco fraseológico” (phraseological calques): exclamations, interjections, adverbial and prepositional expressions and locutions, conversational formulae, idiomatic expressions, fixed phrases, etc. Pragmatic elements are outside the scope of this study
- Paronymic semantic Anglicisms [those cases in which the meaning of a traditional Spanish word is affected by the English influence (the word acquires a new sense, a sense its English paronym has)] and semantic calques (those instances in which the English model is translated, and there is no direct etymological relationship between the English word and its Spanish translation, although they can have the same “étimo último”: for example, to channel/ canalizar)⁷
- Abbreviations with no specification on what they stand for

With the purpose of using a representative and balanced corpus of the Spanish contemporary press, as wide as possible, and that included a great variety of copies (of national as well as local newspapers, generalist and specialized ones, etc.), I chose the *Corpus de Referencia del Español Actual*.

The CREA consists of a vast number of texts extracted from different sources and held electronically. It is freely available at www.rae.es and stores one hundred and sixty million forms approximately. It covers a temporal span that goes from 1975 until 2004 and an array of oral (10%) as well as written (90%) texts produced in all the Spanish-speaking countries. The written part has been selected from books, newspapers, journals, magazines, and miscellaneous sources, and its documents are classified according to the following parameters: chronological, geographical, and thematic.

⁷ “Étimo último”: For Pratt (1980), a landmark in the study of English borrowings adopted by Spanish, Anglicisms are only those words whose “étimo inmediato” (i.e. the language from which they have been taken directly, no matter the languages in which they have been employed in their previous history; cf. “étimo último”, i.e. the first and most remote tongue in which the word was coined, normally Latin or Greek) is the English language. On the contrary, Lorenzo Criado (1996) collects words that come from English, directly or through other languages.

Due to the fact that I aimed to perform searches in a limited part of this huge corpus, its texts were filtered by:

- Chronology: 2001 – 2004
- Medium: Newspapers
- Geography: Spain

Figure 1. Screenshot of CREA’s searching interface.

As can be seen in Figure 1, the boxes for “Author” and “Work” were left empty, since I was not looking for literary pieces. In relation to the topic, I was interested in obtaining instances of all the thematic areas included in CREA. The box “Consulta” is to type the searching form. The section of the CREA I have employed (2001 – 2004, Spain, press, all topics) consists of 5,836,589 words.

Considering the chronological period established, it must be reminded that Rodríguez Segura (1998) compiled her Anglicisms database in the 1990s. Thus, the years 2001 – 2004, which came immediately afterwards, are a good

selection to check the actual use of the English words she collected (which ones have spread and which ones have not, contexts, frequencies, etc.). Furthermore, this temporal segment is relevant because it refers to the first five years of the 21st century.⁸

Following a systematic and consistent procedure, all the concordances I obtained were copied into an Excel document, which comprised five columns:⁹

- Anglicism
- CREA_number of tokens
- Concordance
- Source
- Topic

In the first one, the Anglicisms were introduced in alphabetical order. They were repeated in every line they appeared (i.e. they were written in the first column of each line that included a concordance of it). This way it would be possible to order the Excel table by different columns afterwards, without losing the information on which word the line refers to.

The second one is filled either with 0 (if no results have been obtained for this Anglicism) or 1 (making reference to the concordance of the word that appears in this line). By doing so, at the end of the column we can obtain the

⁸ They are the only years belonging to the 21st century that are included in the CREA. I thought about the possibility of using the CORPES XXI [*Corpus del Español del Siglo XXI* (21st Century-Spanish Corpus, my translation)], which nowadays covers texts from 2001 to 2012. Nevertheless, finally I rejected this option because, in relation to the thematic classification, it only considers general fields, whereas the CREA divides these broader categories into subfields as well. Owing to the fact that I intended to focus on areas such as “sports” or “computing” (that appeared in the lower level of the taxonomy), I preferred the latter corpus.

⁹ It must be noted that, from time to time, among the concordances that are obtained after searching for an Anglicism, some of them appear more than once. In these cases I have adopted the following procedure: if they dated from the same day, were found in the same newspaper, and were employed in texts belonging to the same thematic area, I have deleted them. Otherwise, they have been maintained. It is particularly relevant the case of two dates, 10/04/2003 and 01/05/2003, in which there are plenty of repeated concordances from the newspaper *El País* (topic: computing). According to the criteria I have established, all of them have been kept because they come from different days.

total number of tokens (of Anglicisms) that have been found in the corpus of journalistic texts.¹⁰

The next section is devoted to the concordances (i.e. ‘a word or phrase and its surrounding co-text’) of the Anglicisms. Thanks to them, we are able to check how the foreign terms appear in real use (shedding light on grammatical elements such as the assignment of gender or the formation of the plural, and also lexical issues like the words with which they collocate in Spanish); *vide* Oncins-Martinez (2012).

The source column informs of the title of the newspaper (or journal) in which the Anglicism appears.¹¹ By working with a reference corpus that embraces such a variety of sources, it has been possible to obtain results from a representative sample of the Spanish contemporary press.

The topic section contains the data on the domain provided by the CREA. It is necessary to clarify that it does not refer to the thematic field in which the Anglicism should be located but to the one where the text in which it appears has been classified in the *Corpus de Referencia del Español Actual*.

¹⁰ According to Oxford Dictionaries online (www.oxforddictionaries.com), a *token* is ‘An individual occurrence of a linguistic unit in speech or writing’. In this case, we refer to every occurrence of an Anglicism, whatever it is. It should be contrasted with *type*, which is defined in the same dictionary as ‘An abstract category or class of linguistic item or unit, as distinct from actual occurrences in speech or writing’. Therefore, “fútbol” and “sándwich” would be two *types* of Anglicisms, while “Juan jugaba al fútbol”, “Elena se comió un sándwich”, “El Madrid y el Barça son dos equipos de fútbol” and “Quiero un sándwich mixto” illustrate the appearance of four *tokens* of Anglicisms.

¹¹ There are some inconsistencies in relation to the categories “periódicos” (newspapers) and “revistas” (journals/magazines) in CREA. As far as I have realised, the following journals are involved: *Arquoweb. Revista de Arqueología en Internet*; *Alfa y Omega. Semanario católico de información*; *Artez. Revista de Artes Escénicas*; *Ciber Revista. enfermeriadeurgencias.com*; *Papeles de la Ingeniería. Boletín de Información del Instituto de Ingeniería de España*. Since it is not just one person (obviously) but a team of researchers that compiles a huge corpus such as CREA, it seems that some of them have considered these titles as “periódicos” while others have encompassed them within the label “revistas”. Probably this is the reason for the mentioned incoherence. To prevent this kind of confusion, it is advisable to establish clear criteria that must be followed by all the members of the working party. Nevertheless, I have decided to follow the CREA structure and I have incorporated into my analysis those results from these journals obtained when searching with the filter “periódicos”.

4. Results and discussion

We must take into account that it has not been possible to state whether the concordances found for an Anglicism appeared in a same document or in several ones. To a certain extent, this problem affects the data about the sources, since maybe there is an Anglicism that arises twenty times in a same text in *El País* (this lexical concentration can be due to the specialized topic the document is about) whereas it is employed sixteen times in sixteen different texts in *El Mundo*, for instance. It would be a mistake to conclude, from these data, that *El País* uses this Anglicism more frequently, in general, than *El Mundo*. However, there is another element that serves as a useful tool for obtaining more reliable results in terms of the frequency with which different newspapers use Anglicisms in their texts: the total number of words from each source that is included in the sample of CREA (2001-2004) constitutes an absolute measure against which the number of tokens obtained for each foreign word can be compared. This way we know that, out of the total number of words, a certain lexical item (the Anglicism) appears x times, and we can calculate the global percentages and frequencies per thousand words for each item.¹²

But let's start by the beginning. First of all, in relation to the source, I have calculated the number of tokens of Anglicisms that appears in each of them. Results are reflected in Table 1. As this table shows, if we take into consideration just the amount of occurrences of Anglicisms in the newspapers (and journals) analysed, the first position is occupied by *El País*. In fact, words of English origin were employed in this source 4261 times. This would be the paper that most frequently employs Anglicisms, followed by *La Razón*

¹² Lexical item: Not all Anglicisms are made up of only one word. Some are formed by two or even three. Therefore, if "CREA, 2001 – 2004, Spain, press" contains 25000 words from a certain newspaper, for instance, and out of them I have found 1320 tokens of Anglicisms, it should be borne in mind that maybe they are not 1320 words. That is why I employ the term *lexical item* (I must thank Dr. Encarnación Hidalgo for her comments on this phenomenon and her suggestion of the term). Although this matter can alter slightly the percentages and frequencies per thousand words obtained, in fact most of the Anglicisms analysed in the present study consists of just one word. Thus, the modifications that results have undergone because of this issue cannot actually be considered as relevant.

(2392), *El Mundo* (1450), *Faro de Vigo* (1232), and *El Norte de Castilla* (858).

Source	N. of tokens of Anglicisms
<i>El País</i>	4261
<i>La Razón</i>	2392
<i>El Mundo</i>	1450
<i>Faro de Vigo</i>	1232
<i>El Norte de Castilla</i>	858
<i>El Diario Vasco</i>	591
<i>ABC</i>	572
<i>Diario de Navarra</i>	373
<i>Artez. Revista de artes Escénicas / Artez. Revista de artes escénicas</i>	337
<i>El Cultural</i>	314
<i>La Luna del siglo XXI</i>	307
<i>Canarias 7</i>	298
<i>As</i>	297
<i>Diario Málaga-Costa del Sol</i>	245
<i>La Voz de Galicia</i>	220
<i>Estrella Digital</i>	166
<i>Informe de Evaluación de Tecnologías Sanitarias</i>	153
<i>La Opinión de Tenerife</i>	133
<i>Diario de Jerez</i>	109
<i>20minutos / 20 Minutos</i>	104
<i>El Periódico Mediterráneo</i>	104
<i>Heraldo de Soria</i>	88
<i>Diario digital de Ferrol</i>	73
<i>El Periódico</i>	73
<i>Marca</i>	73

<i>El Periódico de Aragón</i>	72
<i>El Adelanto</i>	71
<i>Diario de Sevilla</i>	70
<i>El Periódico Extremadura</i>	63
<i>Metro Directo</i>	63
<i>Diario de Arousa</i>	61
<i>Última Hora Digital</i>	54
<i>Hispania Nova. Revista de Historia Contemporánea</i>	45
<i>La Voz de Asturias</i>	44
<i>Ideal</i>	42
<i>Información</i>	34
<i>Papeles del Psicólogo</i>	30
<i>Ciudad de Alcoy</i>	29
<i>Turismo@Polibea</i>	26
<i>El Diario Montañés</i>	21
<i>El Heraldo de Aragón</i>	21
<i>El Pueblo de Ceuta</i>	21
<i>ArqueoWeb. Revista sobre /de Arqueología en Internet</i>	19
<i>Comunidad Escolar</i>	19
<i>La Voz de la Afición</i>	19
<i>Infojardín</i>	13
<i>Odiseo Revista de Historia</i>	13
<i>Melilla Hoy. El periódico de Melilla</i>	11
<i>Boletín Galileo</i>	10
<i>Ciber Revista. enfermeriadeurgencias.com / Ciber revista. Enfermeriadeurgencias.com / Ciberrevista. Enfermería de urgencias</i>	10
<i>Diario Palentino Digital</i>	9
<i>Alfa y Omega. Semanario católico de información</i>	7
<i>Papeles de la Ingeniería. Boletín de Información del Instituto de Ingeniería de España / Papeles de la ingeniería</i>	7

<i>El periódico Popular</i>	4
<i>Boletín Epidemiológico Semanal</i>	3
TOTAL N. OF TOKENS	15734

Table 1. Source and number of tokens.¹³

However, this interpretation of results forgets a key element of the analysis, namely the total number of words that the samples of the sources (2001 – 2004, Spain) contain. It goes without saying that 2000 out of 7000 is not the same as 2000 out of 23000. Therefore, more important than the raw data are the percentages and the frequencies per thousand words that can clarify the real presence and weight of foreign lexical items in each source (*vide supra*).¹⁴ As we all know, it is essential to normalise the frequencies we obtain. Hence, in Table 2 there is a more reliable picture of the situation.

Now, the positions occupied by the newspapers (and journals) included in CREA have changed considerably. The first place in the ranking is for *La Luna del siglo XXI*, with 10.11/1000 words. In the

¹³ The column *sources* includes the cases in which there are variations in the spelling of the newspapers' (or journals') names. In addition to this, it should be clarified that the supplements as well as the digital editions that some papers have are included within their "general" names, e.g.:

- "ABC Cultural" is encompassed under the label *ABC*
- "A tu Salud. Suplemento de Salud de La Razón Digital" is covered by *La Razón*
- Ideal Digital > *Ideal*

The only exception here is *La Luna del Siglo XXI* (a supplement of *El Mundo*) since the CREA does not specify that it is a supplement; on the contrary, this corpus considers it as an independent publication. Furthermore, due to the high number of Anglicisms I have found in it, I think it deserves a space for its own. It should also be noticed that those titles which have only a digital edition (such as *Estrella Digital*) maintain the word "digital" in their name.

¹⁴ Percentages and frequencies per thousand words entail the same type of operation, the only difference being the fact that in the first case we refer to 100 whereas the second points at 1000. In corpus linguistics, the latter is more commonly provided than the former. Moreover, in this case the quantities obtained make it advisable to calculate the frequencies per thousand words as well.

second and third ones there are two papers specialized on the sports field: *As* (9.70/1000) and *Marca* (8.63/1000). The fourth position is filled by *Turismo@Polibea* (6.52/1000), whereas the fifth one is covered by *Diario Málaga-Costa del Sol* (6.23/1000). None of them coincides with the top five sources in Table 1. As a matter of fact, *El País* is now in the 11th place, *La Razón* in the 22nd, *El Mundo* in the 14th, *Faro de Vigo* in the 37th and *El Norte de Castilla* in the 30th one.

As possible reasons for the appearance of these five sources in the top positions of the ranking, the following influencing factors can be stated:

1. The contents covered by *La Luna del Siglo XXI* (music, fashion, books, television, humour, photography, etc.; in sum, a wide range of artistic and cultural expressions) have proved to be very prone to the use of Anglicisms. In fact, many of these spheres are highly influenced by English-speaking countries, and this is reflected in the language. Besides, including a reference to the 21st century in the name of the supplement conveys a sense of topicality and modernity. Introducing words of English origin can help to transmit this impression due to the positive connotations this language has (if authors use English elements in their texts, they are considered as more up to date and more prestigious by their readers).

2. and 3. The fact that *As* and *Marca* are newspapers devoted to the field of sports makes them be a perfect source for Anglicisms. This statement is explained in Rodríguez González (2012, p. 318) when he comments upon the fact that “buena parte de los deportes que se practican hoy, y de manera especial los que cuentan con más seguidores y más impacto mediático, son de origen anglo-norteamericano” [A great number of the sports practiced nowadays, especially those with more followers and media impact, are of Anglo-North American origin (my translation)].

4. According to the position that *Turismo@Polibea* has obtained, tourism is a field in which a considerable number of Anglicisms is em-

ployed, which can be explained by referring to Rocamora Abellán's (1999, p.131) words: "El turismo es un sector que se transforma constantemente, aparecen en el mercado nuevos productos casi cada temporada estival lo que, paulatina pero constantemente, va afectando al lenguaje". As a matter of fact, the name of the activity (the word "turismo") is an Anglicism itself.

5. The place occupied by *Diario Málaga-Costa del Sol* is perfectly understandable due to the extralinguistic circumstances affecting the geographical area where this newspaper is published. First, floods of tourists arrive at the province of Malaga, in the South of Spain, every year. And, what is more, a number of British people lives in this part of the Andalusian coast.

	Source	N. of words	N. of tokens of Anglicisms	Percentage	Frequency per thousand words
1	<i>La Luna del siglo XXI</i>	30362	307	1,01	10,11
2	<i>As</i>	30625	297	0,97	9,70
3	<i>Marca</i>	8461	73	0,86	8,63
4	<i>Turismo@Polibea</i>	3985	26	0,65	6,52
5	<i>Diario Málaga-Costa del Sol</i>	39323	245	0,62	6,23
6	<i>La Opinión de Tenerife</i>	21594	133	0,62	6,16
7	<i>El Diario Montañés</i>	4010	21	0,52	5,24
8	<i>20minutos / 20 Minutos</i>	19950	104	0,52	5,21
9	<i>El Periódico</i>	14108	73	0,52	5,17
10	<i>Metro Directo</i>	12978	63	0,49	4,85
11	<i>El País</i>	1106338	4261	0,39	3,85
12	<i>El Periódico de Aragón</i>	19048	72	0,38	3,78
13	<i>Diario de Sevilla</i>	20790	70	0,34	3,37
14	<i>El Mundo</i>	436856	1450	0,33	3,32
15	<i>La Voz de Galicia</i>	68800	220	0,32	3,20
16	<i>Estrella Digital</i>	54013	166	0,31	3,07
17	<i>Última Hora Digital</i>	18095	54	0,30	2,98

18	<i>Artez. Revista de artes Escénicas /Artez. Revista de artes escénicas</i>	113013	337	0,30	2,98
19	<i>Diario de Jerez</i>	38087	109	0,29	2,86
20	<i>ABC</i>	212655	572	0,27	2,69
21	<i>Canarias 7</i>	113539	298	0,26	2,62
22	<i>La Razón</i>	936392	2392	0,26	2,55
23	<i>El Diario Vasco</i>	234897	591	0,25	2,52
24	<i>Diario de Navarra</i>	148607	373	0,25	2,51
25	<i>Ciudad de Alcoy</i>	11667	29	0,25	2,49
26	<i>Diario digital de Ferrol</i>	29799	73	0,24	2,45
27	<i>El Adelanto</i>	29608	71	0,24	2,40
28	<i>El Heraldo de Aragón</i>	8896	21	0,24	2,36
29	<i>Infojardín</i>	5568	13	0,23	2,33
30	<i>El Norte de Castilla</i>	387149	858	0,22	2,22
31	<i>Información</i>	15414	34	0,22	2,21
32	<i>Ideal</i>	19214	42	0,22	2,19
33	<i>El Pueblo de Ceuta</i>	9677	21	0,22	2,17
34	<i>Diario de Arousa</i>	28178	61	0,22	2,16
35	<i>Heraldo de Soria</i>	41409	88	0,21	2,13
36	<i>El Periódico Mediterráneo</i>	49447	104	0,21	2,10
37	<i>Faro de Vigo</i>	591268	1232	0,21	2,08
38	<i>El Cultural</i>	168814	314	0,19	1,86
39	<i>El Periódico Extremadura</i>	34099	63	0,18	1,85
40	<i>La Voz de Asturias</i>	26228	44	0,17	1,68
41	<i>Boletín Galileo</i>	7321	10	0,14	1,37
42	<i>Informe de Evaluación de Tecnologías Sanitarias</i>	116875	153	0,13	1,31
43	<i>Papeles de la Ingeniería. Boletín de Información del Instituto de Ingeniería de España / Papeles de la ingeniería</i>	5958	7	0,12	1,17

44	<i>Papeles del Psicólogo</i>	27685	30	0,11	1,08
45	<i>Diario Palentino Digital</i>	9141	9	0,10	0,98
46	<i>Comunidad Escolar</i>	20875	19	0,09	0,91
47	<i>Melilla Hoy. El periódico de Melilla</i>	12933	11	0,09	0,85
48	<i>La Voz de la Afición</i>	34952	19	0,05	0,54
49	<i>Boletín Epidemiológico Semanal</i>	6908	3	0,04	0,43
50	<i>El periódico Popular</i>	10369	4	0,04	0,39
51	<i>Ciber Revista. enfermeriadeurgencias.com / Ciber revista. Enfermeriadeurgencias.com / Ciberrevista. Enfermería de urgencias</i>	25971	10	0,04	0,39
52	<i>Hispania Nova. Revista de Historia Contemporánea</i>	132070	45	0,03	0,34
53	<i>Odiseo Revista de Historia</i>	51118	13	0,03	0,25
54	<i>Alfa y Omega. Semanario católico de información</i>	34238	7	0,02	0,20
55	<i>ArqueoWeb. Revista sobre/de Arqueología en Internet</i>	177214	19	0,01	0,11
	TOTAL N.	5836589	15734		

Table 2. Real presence of Anglicisms in the different sources

Finally, I must confirm or reject, in light of the findings, the hypotheses stated at the beginning of this paper. I will discuss them, basing my arguments on the results obtained in the present study.

- Hypothesis 1: There are some sources in which no Anglicisms are used.

This statement has turned out to be false. In all the newspapers (and journals) included in the category “periódicos” in the CREA (2001 – 2004, Spain)

some Anglicisms have been employed (*vide* Table 1), which proves the spread of Anglicisms in the Spanish press at present.

- Hypothesis 2: In relation to ideological differences, *El País* contains more Anglicisms than *La Razón* and *ABC*.

This hypothesis has proved to be true. *El País*, in the 11th position of the scale, has a frequency of 3.85/1000 words. On the other hand, *La Razón* and *ABC* are very close to each other, the former in place 22 with 2.55/1000 words and the latter in number 20 and having a frequency of 2.69/1000 words. These findings suggest that there is a correlation between the ideological stance of the newspaper and its openness towards Anglicisms, being the more conservative ones less receptive to the introduction of foreign words. That said, *La Razón* and *ABC* are far from being located at the bottom of the ranking (*vide* Table 2).

- Hypothesis 3: *As* and *Marca*, being newspapers specialized in sports, are the sources in which more tokens of Anglicisms appear.

This statement is not completely true. The first position is occupied by *La Luna del siglo XXI*. But right after it both of them come (*vide* Table 2). The fact that they occupy such high places in the classification (the 2nd and 3rd positions respectively) confirms the idea that sports is a discursive field prone to the use of English loanwords.

5. Conclusion

By applying corpus analysis when studying the employment of Anglicisms in the press, we are able to know the sources that more (and less) frequently introduce words of English origin. Results have shown that in *La Luna del siglo XXI*, *As*, *Marca*, *Turismo@Polibea*, and *Diario Málaga-Costa del Sol* the weight and relevance of the use of Anglicisms is higher than in the rest of newspapers (and journals).

It goes without saying that the results obtained in this work constitute tendencies and cannot be generalised, since they are based just on the sample I have analysed. Nevertheless, having chosen to study a corpus characterised

by being a representative and balanced sample of the Spanish contemporary press (it includes 55 different sources), we have the guarantee that the results obtained in this piece of research are a reliable reflect of the span I have dealt with (2001 – 2004).

In addition, it should be taken into consideration that, in this study, I have limited the Anglicisms covered to those collected by Rodríguez Segura (1998). Therefore, there can be other words of English origin in the journalistic texts stored in the CREA (2001 – 2004, Spain) that I have not focused on. However, the total number of different Anglicisms I have searched for amounts to 2198 (*vide* Appendix below), which constitutes a very comprehensive sample of English loanwords.

This paper has highlighted the complexities that must be taken into account when carrying out the kind of corpus analysis I have presented, since lack of attention to issues such as the need for normalising the frequencies can lead to inaccurate results.

Finally, it would be interesting to consult, in a future piece of research, the style guides of those sources that most frequently employ Anglicisms, in order to check whether the advices provided by these books in relation to the inclusion of loanwords are implemented or not.

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APPENDIX

Anglicisms searched for (selected from Rodríguez's (1998) wordlist)

(en) off, ABS, acces time (sic), accesar, ace, acid, acid house, acid-aficionado, acondicionador de aire, acquaplanning, acre, action painter, action painting, acuaplanning, acustic club (sic), adicción (a las drogas), Advanced Vehicle System, aerobic, aerobic, aerobús, aeroclub, aerolínea, affirmative language, afro, after games, after hours, afterpunk, after-shave, after-shaves, aftersun, agility, agribusiness, agropop, aguaplanning, airbag, airbus, aire acondicionado, aislacionismo, aislacionista, alien, all star, All Star Game, alocatar, alta fidelidad, alto standing, ambient, amigable con el usuario, amplificador, animatronics, Anti Block System, antiapartheid, anti-dive, antidopaje, anti-doping, antiestrés, antifans, antistress, anti-trust, anti-zappineo, anti-zapping, apartheid, aparthotel, aparthoteles, approach, aqua training, aquaplanning, arcade, arty, asesino en serie, assistant manager, ataches, ATP, audiotex, auditor, autocar, autocares, autocue, autocues, autoestop, autofocus, autolink, autoreverse, autorickshaw, autorickshaws, autorreverse, autostop, autotracking, AVS, baby, baby boom, baby sitter, babylonmanía, backgammon, background, backstreetmanía, backup, bacon, bad-lands, badminton, baffle, banana split, banners, bar, bar towel, barbacoa, barbacuá, barman, barra inteligente, base (salto base), base de datos, BASIC, basket, básquet, basket control, basketmanía, bas-kit, basquet, basset, basset hound, batir un récord, baton twirler, battletech, beat, beat 'em up, beat generation, beatle, beatlemanía, beatles, beautiful, beautiful people, beauty case, beauty people, bebida inteligente, bed & breakfast, beedies, beep, beeper, behaviorismo, behaviorista, béisbol, bermudas, best-seller, bet.seller (sic), bicicleta de montaña, bicicross, bicoid, big band, big one, big-bang, biker, bikini, bikinis, bingo, biofeedback, bioman, bioplastic, bio-spray, bip-bip, birdie, birdies, biscúter, bistec, bit, bitico, bitmap, bits, bits generation, biutiful (sic), black, black power, blackjack, blazer, blazers, blend of USA, blister, bloc, bloces, block language, blocs, blood-shift, blue chip, blue jean, blue jeans, blue stocking, blues, bluesman, bluesy, blusero, blush, bobby, bodies, body, body (el body), body art, body building, bodyboard, bodyboarding, bodybuilding, body-building, bodymilk, bodys, bodysilk, bogey, bogeys, boicot, boicoteo, bol, bonus, bonus poll, boock, book, booker, booking, boom, border collie, boss, botafumeiroman, bottombra, bourbon, box and one, box office, boxeador, boxear, boxes, boxístico, boy, boy scout, bracelete (sic), brainstorming, brake dance, brandymanía, breafing, break, breakdance, breakthrough, briefing, brik, brit, british, British Dominion of Gibraltar, brit-pop, broadcast, broadcasting, brocker, broker, brokerage, brother, brothers, browser, brunch,

brushing, brushings, buckminsterfullereno, buckyball, buckytubo, buddy movie, budin, buffer, building, building society, bulldog, bulldozer, bulldozers, bumerán, bungalow, bungalows, bunker, búnker, búnkeres, bunkerizarse, burger, burn out, burnout, burn-out, bus, bus local, bus-bob, buscador de senderos, business class, business school, business to business, businessman, business-model, buy-out, by pass, bypass, by-pass, byroniano, byte, bytes, cabezas rapadas, cacaburger, cache, cache, CAD, café society, cake, californian sun, call girl, call girls, calls, cambiar el chip, camcorder, camcorders, camel, cámel, cámping, camping gas, cámpings, campus, Cancellor of the Exchequer, candies, cannabis, canoeing, canyoning, car audio, Car Hi-Fi, caravanning, cardigan, cárdigan, cardiotraining, cartridge, cascos azules, cash, cash & carry, cash flow, cast, casting, cásting, casting couch, casual wear, catcher, catering, cátering, cattering, cazatalentos, CD, CD-Audio, CD-I, CD-ROM, CD's, cederrom, cederromes, cederrón, celler, cerdo de Guinea, cerdo guineano, cermet, cermets, challenge, challenges, chance, charlestón, chart, charter, chárter, chat, cheap magazine, check-in, checkpoint, cheerleader, cheerleaders, cheeseburger, chequear, chequeo, chessball, chewing gum, chief executive, chief executive officer, chip, chipset, chopped, chopped-beef, chopped-pork, chop-suey, chorus, chou, chouleaders, Chrismats [sic], Christmas cake, Christmas shops, Christopher lait, chunking, chut, chutar, chute, CIA, cibacrons, ciberman, ciberpunk, ciber-rock, ciborg, cicloscooter, cinemascope, CISC, city, clan, clase business, clasicmanía, clearing, clergyman, click, climatronic, climax, clinero, clip, clip-art, clippear, clipper, clipping, clown, clownesco, clowns, club, clubes, clubs, cluster, clúster, CM, CNN, coach, cociente intelectual, cockney, cocktail, cóctel, coke, cold shoulder, collateral damage, college, colorprinting, combot, comedia de situación, comic, comic book, comida basura, comida rápida, Commonwealth, compacdis, compact, compact disc, Complete Set of Instructions, composite, compositing, compost, compostable, computador, computadora, computer, computer-to-plate, comunicacional, confirming, conservativo, consulting, consultoría, container, containers, cookies, cool, cooler, coolies, cop, copia dura, cops, copyright, core, córner, córnern, cornflakes, corporate rightsizing, correo electrónico, cótel [sic], cottage, cottages, country, country rock, cowboy, cowboys, CPU, crack, crak, crash, crash test, crash-sensor, crashtest, crash-test, Crew Resources Management (CRM), crol, crolista, crol, crooner, cross, cross training, crossbar, cuásar, culling, cult band, cup, curry, custom, cutter, cyberjeans, cybermall, ciberpunk, ciborg, D.J., D.J.'s, dance, dandi, dandy, dandy-hippy, Darling, daseinanalysis, daseinanalyst, DAT, data-link, data-mining, data-warehouse, day pack, DAZ, DCC, DDC, DDD, de mood a mood, deadline, dealer, dealers, dealing, debugear, decibelio, demo, demolition man, denim, derby, desflashado, design, desktop, destroy, destroyer, destroyers, differently abled, digital audio tape, digital scan, digital video, digital-VHS, dinner, dinomanía, direccionar, dirty chic, dirty

protets (sic), dirty realism, disablear, discapacitado, disc-jockey, discman, disco compacto, disco digital, disco duro, disco music, discount, diskette, diskettera, diskettes, display, disquete, disquetera, disquetes, distress, dithering, diving, DNA, dólar, donkey boys, donut, donuts, dopado, dopaje, dopante, dopar, doparse, doping, dopping, double face, downshifting, downtown, DPI, drag queen, Drag Racing, dragmanía, dragsters, dream team, dribbling, driblar, dries, drill, drills, drink, drive, driver, drogadicción, drogadicto, drogas de diseño, drop, drops, drugstore, DSP, duffel coat, dummies, dummy, dumper, dumpin, dúplex, DV, DVD, DVD-ROM, D-VHS, eagle, eagles, earthshoes, easy care, easy mop, easy-rider, easy-riders, e-business, e-cash, eco-pack, ecu, ECU, ecus, ECUS , edutainment, eggosaurio, egotismo, eigenface, electribike, electrochoque, electroshock, elepé, elepés, e-mail, e-money, emoticons, en el aire, en vivo, enablear, encuestas de salida, equity retreat, escanear, escaner, escáner, escaners, escáners, escay, escúter, escúteres, eslipada, eslogan, esloganes, esmoquin, esmoquin, esnifar, esnob, esnobismo, esnobista, espídico, espónsor, esponsorización, esponsorizar, esquí, esquiador, esquiar, esquigolf, esquinas parlantes, essential Egypt, establishment, estándar, estándares, estandarización, estandarizar, estéreo, estrellato, estrés, estresada, estresado, estresante, estresor, estripista, eurobasket, eurobuilding, euromárketing, eustress, exit, expel, extropianos, extropians, eye-fate, eye-liner, eye-linner, factoring, fair play, fan, fanes, fans, fanzine, FAQ, far west, fashion, fashion victim, fashion victims, fast, fast food, fast-forward, fax, faxear, faxes, FBI, fed funds, feedback, feeling, feelings, fender, ferry, fifty-fifty, film, filmación, filmar, filme, filmes, filmlets, films, final cut-off time, final four, finger, first termic, fitness, five o'clock tea, five step, flash, flashazo, flashback, flasheado, flashear, flashes, flatlock, flavor, fleemarkets, flirt, flirtear, flirteo, floppy, floppy disk, FM, folclor, folclore, folclórica, folclórico, folclorista, folk, folkie, folklore, folklórica, folklórico, folky, follow-up, footbag, footing, for sale, Foreign Office [sic], forever, forfait, forfaits, formatear, formula writers, forward, fourballs, foursomes, foxterrier, fox-trot, FPS, franchising, freaks, free, free ball, free cinema, free enterprise economy, free float, free lance, free lance killer, free rider, free-bol, freedom, freelance, free-lance, fretos, freeware, french cachette, fresbee, friends, friqui, fruit cake, FSH, full contact, full duplex, full time, fullereno, fun bike, funboard, fundraising, fun-fly, funk, funkier, funky, funny car, funware, fútbol, futbolero, fútboles, futbolista, fut-voley, gadgets, gag, gags, gai, gais, galaxy rock, gangster, gángster, gangsteriles, gangsterismo, gangsters, gángsters, gánster, gánsteres, gánsters, gap, garage rock, gas oil, gasoil, gas-oil, gasóleo, gated communities, gay, gays, GB, gel-body, General Management Admissions Test, general store, gente guapa, gentleman, gentry, Geographical Magachin [sic], ghetto, gigabyte, gigabytes, gigaoctet, gigaoctets, gimlet, ginger ale, ginseng, gin-tonic, gintonics, girl power, glam, glam-rock, glamour, glamouroso, glamrock, glam-rock, glamuroso, globe trotters, GMAT, godspell, gol, golaverage, golden retriever, golden

retriever, golden share, goleada, goleador, goles, golf, golfista, gong, gore, goremanía, goretex, gospel, grammy, green, green belt, green machine, grill, grind, grogui, groupie, groupware, grunge, guest star, gueto, guonderbrá, guru, gym-jazz, hacker, hall, Halloween, halter, hamburguesa, hamburguesera, hamburguesería, hammer , hándicap, discapacado, handling, happening , happy-, happy coats, happy end, happy hour, happy meal, happy sixties, hard, hard disc, hard discount, hard disk, hard rock, hard-core, hardware, harris, HDD, headhunter, heavy, heavy metal, heavy rock, heli-esquí, heli-skiing, helpware, hi fi, hidrobob, hidrofoil, hidrospeed, high school, high society, high speed, high tec, high tech, high yielder, highware, hill billy, hip hop, hip hop swing, hiper, hipermedia, hipers, hippie, hippies, hippiesco, hippioso, hippismo, hippizante, hippy, hit, hit parade, hobbie, hobbies, hobby , hobbys, hockey, HOG, holding, hollywoodesco, hollywoodiano, hollywoodiense, home run, homeland, homeless, homepage, hooligan, hooligang, hooligans, hora feliz, hot dog, hot line, hot spots, hot-ball, house, house generation, hovercraft, HTML, http, hub, husky, hustler, iceberg (ser algo la punta del iceberg), implementar, imprinting, imput, imputs, in (estar in), in/out, indexar, indi, indie , indoor, infoshow, inicializar, inner city, input, inputs, interactivo, intercity, intercooler, interesoteniendo, interface, interfase, interfaz, internet, interviú, intranet, inusual, IRA, Ironman, ítem, jacksonmanía, jacuzzi, jam session, jazz, jazzístico, jazzman, jazz-rock, jeans, jeanswear, jeep , jerséi, jerséis, jerseises [sic], jersey, jerseys, jet, jet boat, jet set, jet society, jet-foil, jetlag, jingle, JIT, jogging, joint venture, jointventure, joint-venture, joystick, joysticks, jr, jr., Juanas Nadie, judo, jumbo, junior, juniors, just-in-time, K.O., kart, karting, karts, ketchup, key symbol, KeyCard, kick boxing, killer, killer kiss, kilobit, kilobyte, kind start, kindergarten, king size, kit, kitch, kitsch, knowbot, know-how, ladies, lady, laight (i.e. light), láit (i.e. light), lambswol, lambswool, land of memory, larger than life, láser, láser disc, láser-com, láseres, lasérico, laser-writer, latin lover, lavavajillas, LBE, lean management, leasing, leggings, leggins, LEM, lentes de contacto, lexical, líder, liderar, liderato, liderazgo, líderes, life line, lifting, light, linkar, lip-fix, lipofiling, lipstick, lising, live, lobbista , lobby, lobbying, lobbysmo, local bus, loft, look, looping, lord, lores, lounge, LP, LPs, lumpen, lúmpen, lumperío, lumperizarse, lunch, lunchable, lurex, machoman, mad max, made in, madmaxista, magazin, magazine, magazines, mail art, mailart, mail-art, mailear, mailing, mailings, major, majors, management, management buy-out, manager, managers, managing director, mapear, máquina house, marca de fábrica, marching band, marine, marines, market markers, marketing, márketing, marketing mix, marketing one-to-one, Mars Environmental Survey, mass media, master, master in business administrastion [sic], masters, match, MB, MBA, Mbyte, Mbytes, MD, MD walkman, MD walkmans, MDs, mecadotecnia, mediático, medical research manager, mega-bit, megabite, megabyte, megabytes, megacarrier, megaoctet, mega-pack, mega-star, megastore,

megatón, megatones, megatop, melting pot, memorabilia, mercadeo, mercado de pulgas, merchandasing, merchandiser, merchandising, MESUR, metal rock, metal sound, microchip, microcyborg, microfalda, micropeeling, microsoft, middle class, mini cooper, minibang, minibasket, minicar, mini-casting, mini-CD, minidisc, minidisks, minifalda, minigolf, mini-Lp, minimal, minimalismo, minimalista, minimarket, minimarkets, minishort, minstrels, MIR, misil, misiles, miss, misses, mister, mites, mitin, mitín, mítin, mitines, mix, mixtura, mobile computing, modem, módem, monis, monises, monster movies, mopa, morphing, motorball, mountain bike, mountain biker, mouse, mouses, MPC business audio, multimedia, multimediático, multivan, music hall, music televisión, must , muteo, N.A., nailon, naked, nanny, NASA, NC, neo-hippie, neo-hippies, neo-hippy, neo-hyppy, NetPC, netting, network computer, network computing, never, New Age, new journalism, new look, new peeling, new wave, news, newsgroup, nickname, niger, nigger, niñóbic, no-clipping, noise, noise-pop, non food, non oil business, nonsense, nonsensuales, non-stop, non-tracking, non-vegetarian, noqueador, noqueadores, noqueo, notebook, number one, nurse, nursería, nylon, off, off the record, offset, offshore, offshore administration, offside, off-sider, oil free, OK, okei, okei Makei, on, on line, on site, on the right track, on the road, one design , op-art, operator, optical, opting-out, orsaid, orsay, óscares, oscars, OTAN, out, outdoor, outing, output, outputs, outsider, overbooking, overbookings, overland, overline, oversize, pacekeepers, pack, pack ergo, packaging, packansing, packing, pad, paddel, padding, paddings, paddle tennis, padel, pádel, padle, pakage show, palo asesino, panties, panty, pantys, papeles de identidad, parapenting, parka, parking, part time, party, party line, passing, passwords, patch, patcheado, patches, patchwork, path, Patient Controlled Anesthesia, pay per view, PC, PC Card, PC exchange, PC master, PC tools, PCA, PCC, PC's, peach, peanut, peanuts, pearcing, pecé, pedigrí, peeling, peep show, peeping show, pen, penalti, penalti, penny magazine, Pepsi board, performance, performances, perkins, permafrost, Personal Communication Computer, personal computer, peterpanismo, petting, phone-box, pick up, picú, piercing, pin, PIN, pinball, ping pong, pin'ups, pipe-line, pit bull, pixel, planking, planning, play, play back, play backs, playback, play-back, playbacks, play-backs, playboy, play-off, play-offs, plotear, plug and play, Plug&Play, plug-in, plug-ins, plum cake, plussing, póker, polaroid, polaroids, pole, pole position, poll (fracaso poll), polving, pompom girls, poney, ponnies, pony, pop, pop corns, pop tarts, pop-art, poper, Poppy Day, pop-rock, póquer, portable, portafolio de productos, poscript, posing strap, post minimal, postal free, poster, póster, pound cake, power, power CD, power ranger, power trío, power-pop, preliminary cut-off time, premier, prensa amarilla, pressing-boxeo, pressing-catch, pre-task, pretty, price smash, prime time, printable, printer, prion, príon, priones, privacidad, procedural, product manager, product manager senior, product placement, progroms, prom, proms, pro-stock, pro-tory, psycho killer, psychokiller,

psycho-killer, pub, pubes, Publish or Perish, pubs, pudin, puenting, pullover, pullovers, punch, punk, punkie, punkis, punk-rock, punkys, putt, putter, putts, puzzle, puzzles, quads, quark, quarks, quásar, quest, quickwheel, racing, rad board, radar, radares, RADSL, rafting, ragtime, rail, rally, rallye, rallyes, rallies, RAM, ramie, ranger, ranking, rap, rapear, rapero, rapper, rappero, rappers, raps, rash, rasta, rating, ratmusket, ravers, RDS, read and return, ready for use, ready to use, reaggea, realidad virtual, realiti, realiti show, realiti-chou, realitichous, realitis-chous, reality, reality show, récord, recordman, red localtalk, Reduced Set of Instructions, réflex, reggae, reggae-rap, relax, remake, remakes, remasterizado, remasterizar, remember, remix, removable, render, rendering, renderizado, renderizar, rent-a-car, renting, repóker, reporting, resetear, resort, restiling, restyling, retrollamada, reverb, reverv, revival, revólver, rewind, RFC, rhithm and blues, rhythm & blues, rhythm n' blues, richshaw, richshaws, rickshaw, rickshaws, riesgohabiente, riffs, rifle, ring, rings, RISC, road movie, roadster, roast beef, robocop, robot, robótica, robotizar, rock, rock and roll, rock indie, rockabilly, rocker, rockerizarse, rockero, rockers, rocketeers, rocketters, rock-soul, rock-star, rock-stars, rol, rollerski, roll-on, roll-over, roof-garden, roquero, rosbif, rotary, rotoscoping, rough, round, round robins, rounds, royal, royals, royalty, rugby, running, rush, rythm and blues, sales representative, salón, saltobasista, sampleado, samplear, sampler, samplers, sampling, sand wedge, sandwich, sandwichera, sandwichería, sandwiches, SAR, sauna, saxofón, scanner, scones for tea, scoop, scooter, scope, scrambled, scrapie, script, script girl, scroll, season, selfmade man, self-service, senior, seniors, sensory vortex, serial killer, servicing a target, set, set point, sets, setter, seventy's, sex-appeal, sexies, sex-shop, sex-symbol, sexy, shakespearanas, shapeCD, share, shares, shareware, sheriff, sherpas, shifting, shilling pamphlets, shimmy, shocking, shopping, short, shorts, short-short story, short-story, show, show business, show room, show woman, showbiz, showgirl, showman, showroom, show-room, showtime, showwoman, show-woman, shuttle, sida, SIDA, sidafobia, sidecar, sidecares, sidecars, sides, sidoso, sillabus, sillonbol, síndrome del quemado, single, singles, sir, sistema de estrellas, sitcom, ska, skai, skatalítico, skate, skateboard, skay, skeet, sketch, sketches, sketches, ski, ski doo, ski kart, ski karting, skidoo, ski-doo, skikart, ski-kart, skikarting, ski-karting, skin, skin abraser, skinhead, skinheads, skimmers, sky, sky surfing, skyline, slalom, slang, slapstick, slice of life, slip, slip-bra, slips, slogan, slot, slowcore, slownly wilderness, slum, SM, SMA, smart card, smart drink, smart drinks, smasheador, smoking, snack, sneakers, snipe, snipers, snipes, snow, snow cycling, snowboard, snuff, snuff movie, snuffmovie, snuff-movie, soccer, soft, Soft Damp, soft discount, softball, software, soul, soul music, soundblaster, soundtrack, speaker, speaker's corner, speakers-corner, special garments, specke, speech, speed, speed wagon, spider, spilberiana, spin, SPLA, splash, spoiler, spoils system, sponsor, sport, sport-chic, sportmanía,

sportswear, sportwear, spot, spots, spray, spread, springer spaniel, sprint, square, squash, SRAM, stablishment, staff, stake, stake holder, stand, standard, stand-by, standing, star, star system, star team, starlet, starlettes, starter, Static Random Access Memory, station wagon, status, status symbol, steadycam, step, stereo, stick, stock, stockholder, stocks, stoniano, stop, storage, store, storyboard, stretch, strech, streep poker, streep-tease, Street, stretch, stresante, stretch, stretching, string, strip, stripper, strip-tease, subnotebook, suburbia, sudden fiction, sueter, sueters, super-bike, superfan, superfreak, superlumpen, superman, supermanes, supermarket, supermarkets, supermodelo, superposter, super-pretty, súper-sport, superstar, super-top, supervan, supervans, superwoman, surf, surfer, surfersónicos, surfing, surfista, SurfMan, surround, suspense, swap, swaps, Swatch car, swing, syllabus, tabloide, tabú, talk show, tándem, tandoori, tap dance, task force, tattoo, taylor, team manager, techno, techno-triller, tecno, tecno-trance, teddy boy, teddy boys, tee, teenage hits, teenager, teenagers, telefilme, teléfono, telemárketing, teleprinter, televisión, teleworking, télex, tener un chip puesto, tenis, tenista, terabyte, terabytes, terminator, terminators, territory manager, test, testing, tetra brik, tetrabra, tetrabrick, tetrabrik, tetra-brik, tex-mex, Thanksgiving (Day) [sic], Thanksgiving (Day), thatcher, thatcheriano, thatcherista, the American way of life, the end, the mail box, the prevailing wind, thrash, thrash metal, thriller, tic, tics, tie break, tiempo completo, a, tiempo parcial, a, timeshifting, timing, tique, tiquet, tobogán, tocadiscos, toffee, toffees, tombstones, tommies, tonner (sic), too big to fail, too much, top drivers, top fuel, top model, top models, top secret, top ten, top-forty, top-less, toppings, tops, topss, tories, tormenta de ideas, tory, total look, touch, tourist liquor permit, toymanía, trabbies, traby, trackball, tracking, trade marketing, trade-off, trail, tráiler, trailers, trainers, trainspotter, transfer, tránsfer, transformers, transistor, trash, trashtalking, treki, trekies, trekking, trekkie, trekkies, trekking, trench coat, trenka, trial, trip, triphop, tripi, tripis, trust, trusts, T-shirt, T-shirts, tumbing, túnel, tuner, Turbo Man, turf, turismo, turista, turística, turístico, turn-over, tweed, twin cam, twin set, twin sets, twinset, twin-set, twinsets, twin-sets, twist, U.S.A., UFO, ufología, ufológico, ufólogo, ultimate fighting, ultra-dry, underground, UNESCO, union jack, unisex, Unites States (sic), unpleasant, unplugged, unplugged, uplifting, USA, vard-sales, váteres, vatio, vegetarian, vending, versus, Very Important Person, Very Important Persons, VESA, video, videocasting, videoclip, videoclub, videogame, videojuego, videowall, videowalls, VIH, village, vinilo, VIP, vip, VIPs, vips, visiting a site, visual merchandising, vivation, voley-playa, voltio, VRC, VRLM, vs, vueling, walkie (talkie), walkman, walkmans, wanted, warm-up, washback, WASP, water, wáteres, waterpolo, waterproof, wavetable, web, WebCam, webcasting, web-sites, weekend, weekender, welfare, West, West End, West Village, western, westerns, wets, wheeling and dealing, whiskeria, whiskey, whisky, whisky on the rocks, white collar, wind surf, windsurf, wind-surf, windsurfing, windsurfista, winer (sic), wiskey,

wisqueria, wonderbra, wonderbragas, wondernalgas, woolmark, work, workflow, working, workshop, World Wide Web, WWF, WWW, yanqui, yanquis, yarda, yé yé, yes, yogur, yonki, yonkie, yonkies, yonkis, yonqui, yonquis, young urbans professionals (sic), yupi, yupis, yuppie, yuppies, yuppillaje, yuppismo, zamp, zamping, zapeo, zapineador, zapineo, zaping, zapiroides, zapista, zapping, zipper, zombie, zombies, zona dadora, zoom